

Synthesis and Biological Activities of Some New 2-(N-Heterocyclo Carboxamidomethyl Thio) Naphth[1,2-d]Oxazoles. Part VI

A. E. ABDEL RAHMAN, H. A. EL-SHERIEF and A. M. MAHMOUD

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Assiut University, Assiut, Egypt

Manuscript received 25 January 1980, revised 12 June 1980, accepted 7 August 1980

A number of 2-(N-thiazolo, pyridino and phenazono carboxamidomethyl thio) naphth[1,2-d]oxazoles (I and II) have been prepared by the interaction of naphth[1,2-d]oxazole-2-thiols with different N-thiazolo-2-chloroacetamides, N-pyridino-2-chloroacetamides and N-phenazono-2-chloroacetamide respectively. The biological activities of the prepared compounds were screened against some strains of bacteria and fungi at a concentration of $10^{-4} M$.

In view of the fact that condensed oxazoles have been of increasing importance due to their industrial and biological properties¹⁻⁶, several thiazole derivatives were also recorded to possess useful anti-inflammatory⁷⁻⁹ and antimicrobial properties. On the other hand, basic acetamides, in which amido-H has been substituted with aromatic¹⁰ or heterocyclic¹¹ moieties have been prepared in large number as potential local anaesthetics. Several basic N-(2-thenyl/furfuryl) acetamides have been patented as analgesic and antispasmodics¹².

It was thought that the combination of an oxazole ring with the well known chemotherapeutic amide substituents and also the valuable thiazole ring might increase these biological activities, the synthesis and structural elucidation of previously unknown 2-(N-heterocyclo carboxamido thio) naphth[1,2-d]oxazoles were undertaken.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 200 G spectrophotometer. UV spectra in spec. pure ethanol were taken on a Pye-Unicam SP 8000 ultraviolet spectrophotometer. The time allowed for the completion of the reaction, and the purity of the prepared compounds were controlled by means of T.L.C. chromatography. Antimicrobial activities were carried out by Mr. H. El-Sharoni, Department of Botany, Faculty of Science, Assiut University.

Naphth[1,2-d]oxazole-2-thiols: Naphth[1,2-d]oxazole-2-thiol and naphth[1,2-d]oxazole-2-thiol-4-sulphonic acid were prepared from 1-amino-2-hydroxynaphthalene and 1-amino-2-hydroxynaphthalene-4-sulphonic acid respectively⁶.

N-Heterocyclo-2-chloroacetamides: These compounds were prepared by the direct interaction of

monochloroacetyl chloride (0.05 mole) with different 2-aminothiazoles¹³, 2- and 3-aminopyridine and 4-aminophenazone (0.05 mole) in acetone as a solvent according to Jacobs *et al* method¹⁴.

2-N-(Heterocyclo carboxamidomethyl thio) naphth[1,2-d]oxazoles (I and II): Thiol compound (0.001 mole) was dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) in the presence of an equivalent amount of KOH and the appropriate N-heterocyclo-2-chloroacetamide (0.001 mole) e.g., N-(2-thiazolo)-2-chloroacetamide was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 30 min, then concentrated and cooled, when a mixture of the crude heterocyclo carboxamido methyl thio naphthoxazole (I and II) and potassium chloride was precipitated. It was acidified with acetic acid, filtered, washed with water to remove KCl and recrystallized from ethanol to give compounds I and II.

- I and II a; thiazole-2
b; 4-phenylthiazole-2
c; 4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-thiazole-2
d; 4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-thiazole-2
e; 4-(*p*-tolyl)-thiazole-2
f; 4-methyl-5-ethylcarboxythiazole-2
g; benzthiazole-2
h; pyridine-2
i; pyridine-3
j; phenazone-4

2-(Carboxymethyl thio) naphth[1,2-d]oxazole(III): It was prepared by the direct interaction of naphth[1,2-d]oxazole-2-thiol (0.05 mole) and monochloroacetic acid (0.07 mole) in ethanol and KOH. The

product was recrystallized from ethanol in about 70% yield, m.p. 205°, R_f 0.92 (benzene and ethylacetate mixture 9 : 1), (Calcd. : C, 60.23 ; H, 3.47 ; N, 5.40 ; S, 12.35. C₁₅H₈NO₂S, Found : C, 60.06 ; H, 3.39 ; N, 5.34 ; S, 12.48).

Reaction of 2-(carboxymethyl thio) naphth[1,2-d]-oxazole(III) with heterocyclic amines : A mixture of compound(III) (0.001 mole), heterocyclic amine (0.001 mole) (2-aminothiazole, 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole, 4-(*p*-bromophenyl)-2-aminothiazole, 4-(*p*-anisyl)-2-aminothiazole, 4-(*p*-tolyl)-2-aminothiazole, 2-aminobenzthiazole and 2-aminopyridine) and N-ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethoxy-1, 2-dihydroquinoline (EEDQ)^{1,6} (0.001 mole) (condensing agent) was dissolved in DMF (4 ml). The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 hours and seeded. The obtained product was recrystallized from ethanol into 2-(N-heterocyclo carboxamidomethyl thio) naphth[1,2-d]oxazole (I a-e, g and h).

Results and Discussion

The present report deals with the preparation of some new 2-(N-heterocyclo carboxamido thio) naphth[1,2-d]oxazoles (I and II) by the interaction of some N-heterocyclo-2-chloroacetamides with appropriate naphth[1,2-d]oxazole-2-thiols.

Thus, N-heterocyclo-2-chloroacetamides were obtained by the direct interaction of monochloroacetyl chloride with different aminothiazoles, aminopyridines and aminophenazone.

Naphth[1,2-d]oxazole-2-thiol and naphth[1,2-d]oxazole-2-thiol-5-sulphonic acid were reacted with N-heterocyclo-2-chloroacetamides in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution to give the corresponding compounds (I and II). In this manner, a number of new types of substituted carboxamidomethyl thio naphthoxazoles have been prepared (Table 1). These compounds are quite stable (and can be recrystallized from organic solvents) as indicated from their resistance to boiling water, to hot 0.1 N hydrochloric acid and to 0.1 N sodium hydroxide solution. It is of interest to record that naphthoxazole sulphonic acid derivatives(II), show an outstanding degree of violet fluorescence in organic solvents (methanol, ethanol, butanol and ethylene glycol).

Compounds (I and II) have been identified by a combination of elemental analysis (Table 1) and spectral data. The ir spectra of compounds (I and II), are characterised by absorption bands at 3420-3350 cm⁻¹ (NH amide)^{1,6}, 1660-1650 (C=O amide)^{1,6}, bands at 1635-1613 cm⁻¹, 1610-1590 and 1550-1540 cm⁻¹ characterised the oxazole system^{5,6,17}. Substituted 2-(N-heterocyclo carboxamidomethyl thio) naphth[1,2-d]oxazoles(II) showed in addition, the bands characteristic of

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS I-II

Compound* No.	m.p. °C	Biological activities			
		<i>Staph.</i> <i>albus</i>	<i>Bacillus</i> <i>megath.</i>	<i>Aspergil.</i> <i>flavus</i>	<i>Penicil.</i> <i>notatum</i>
Ia	245-56	+	+	++	+++
Ib	305-7				
Ic	135-36	+++	++	++	++
Id	228-30	+	++	++	+++
Ie	310d.				
Ig	115-16	++	++	++	++
Ih	163-64	+++	+++	+++	++
Ij	192-94				
IIa	180-2	+++	+++	+++	+++
IIb	270-72				
IIc	199-200	+++	++	+	+++
IId	>360	+	+++	+++	+++
IIe	>360				
IIi	260-65d				
IIg	168-69	+++	++	++	+
IIh	249-50	+++	+++	++	+
IIi	309-10	+++	+++	+++	++
IIj	>360	+	+++	+	-

* Compounds (I) and (II) were obtained in 70-80% and 50% yields respectively.

+, ++ and +++ equal to about 20%, 40% and 75% inhibition effect respectively.

All the compounds gave consistent C, H and N analysis.

substituent groups, e.g., two vibration bands at 1060-1050 and 650 cm⁻¹ for the sulphonic group^{1,6}. The uv spectra of naphthoxazole compounds (I and II, a-i) showed three λ_{max} at 280-290, 300-320 and 330-345 nm similar to substituted naphthoxazoles⁵.

On the other hand, 2-(N-heterocyclo carboxamidomethyl thio)-naphth[1,2-d]oxazoles (I a-e, g and h) could also be obtained through another synthesising route. That is by condensation of the prepared 2-(carboxymethyl thio) naphth[1,2-d]oxazole(III) with different aminothiazoles and/or aminopyridines in the presence of N-ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethoxy-1, 2-dihydroquinoline (EEDQ) as condensing agent^{1,4} and DMF as a solvent.

The identity of compounds (I a-e, g and h) obtained by the two mentioned methods were established by their m.p., mixed m.p., T.L.C (benzene and ethylacetate mixture 9 : 1) and ir absorption spectra.

Antimicrobial activities : The antimicrobial activities of the prepared compounds of the types (I and II) were tested *in vitro* for the biological activities against a variety of bacteria^{1,6}, such as, *Staphy. albus* and *Bacillus megatherium* and against fungi^{1,6}, such as, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Penicillium notatum*. The results of the screened compounds show from a little (20%) to a strong (75%) inhibition at a concentration of 10⁻⁴M.

The more strong active compounds against *Staphy. albus* are (Ie, h and IIa, g, h), against *Bacillus megatherium* (Ih and IIh, j), against *Aspergillus flavus* (Ia, e, h and IIa, d, h, i), and against *Penicillium notatum* (Ia, d and IIa, c, d).

References

1. L. LATZ, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **75**, 712 ; *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, **19**, 756.
2. M. HINRICH, G. CHRISTIAN and SCH. HARALD (Henkel und Cie. G. m. b. H), *Ger. offen.* 2, 164, 851 (Cl. CO7d, A 611) 05 Jul (1973) ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1973, **79**, 92199.
3. SCH. MAX and D. MAX (CIBA Ltd.) Swiss 497, 121 (Cl. A. Oln), 30 Nov. (1970) ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, **75**, 20387.
4. M. HINRICH, B. HORST and K. GUENTER (Henkel and Cie, G.m.b.H), *Ger. Offen.* 2, 024, 052 (Cl. CO. 7d) 09 December (1971) ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1972, **75**, 72506.
5. A. M. OSMAN, H. A. H. EL-SHERIEF and A. M. MAHMOUD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 293.
6. A. M. OSMAN, A. M. MAHMOUD and H. A. H. EL-SHERIEF, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **17B**, 22.
7. S. UMIO, I. UEDA, Y. SATO and H. KAWACHI, *Jap. Pat.* 7, 121, 020, 14 Jan. 1971 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, **75**, 129799.
8. R. J. CLARK and F. F. STEPHENS, *Brit. Pat.*, 1, 080, 246, 23 August 1967 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, **68**, 95, 804.
9. J. WADA, T. SUZUKI, M. IWASAKI, H. MIYAMITSU, S. UENO and M. SHIMIZU, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1973, **16**, 930.
10. LOFGREN and LUNDQUIST, *U. S. 2*, 441, 498 (1948) *Chem. Abs.*, 1948, **42**, 6378.
11. P. N. BHARGAVA and M. R. CHAURASIA, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1969, **58**, 896.
12. ETIENNE SZARVASI and LILIANE NEUVY, *Fr. 1*, 261, 280 (1961) ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, **56**, 10110.
13. R. M. DODSON and L. C. KING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2242 ; L. C. KING and R. J. HLAVACK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 3722.
14. W. A. JACOBS and M. HEIDELBERGER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **93**, 1439.
15. B. BELLEAU and G. MALEK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 1651.
16. L. J. BELLAMY, the infrared spectra of complex molecules, 2nd ed. (Methuen, London), 1958.
17. P. BASSIGNANA, C. COGROSSI and M. GANDINO, *Spectrochim. acta*, 1963, **19**, 1885.
18. J. G. VINCENT and H. W. VINCENT, *Prac. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1944, **55**, 162.
19. G. W. IRVING, *J. Bact.*, 1946, **52**, 101.